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Hiding and nesting behavior of *Stenocercus roseiventris* Duméril & Bibron, 1837 (Reptilia: Tropiduridae)

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S *tenocercus roseiventris* is an inhabitant of tropical rainforest in southwestern Amazonia (Brazil, Peru, Bolivia and northern Argentina; Ribeiro-Junior 2015). Fritts (1974) assumed it would occur in rocky habitats, similar to other lizards with a spiny tail. However, other authors (e.g. Mertens 1942; Meede 1984; Duellman 2005) reported the lizard using holes in tree trunks, logs and buttresses, or holes in the ground as hiding places in forest habitats. Hoogmoed (pers. comm.) collected a specimen (RMNH 25697) in primary forest in Panguana, Peru, on a hollow log in which it took refuge and reappeared after some time. Meede (1984) also reported that a male and a female could be observed on trunks only a few meters apart. During an ex-

pedition in Acre, Brazil, we collected six specimens (4 females and 2 males) of *S. roseiventris* and our observations agree with those in these later studies, refuting the idea that *S. roseiventris* is linked to rocky habitats. We also add observations on its nesting behavior.

The lizards were observed in undisturbed terra firme forest in the Juruá River Basin, near (in W-NW direction) Porto Walter, Acre (8°15' S, 72°46' W). We worked from a field camp actively searching an area of approximately 1 km² of the forest as part of a biodiversity survey between 6 February and 18 April 1996, during the rainy season (see Vitt & Avila-Pires 1998 for a more detailed description of the studied area).

Stenocercus roseiventris was observed between 3 March and 17 April, always during the day. Of the six specimens observed, one (female, OMNH 37045) was on the ground and ran toward a fallen trunk, entering a hole in it. A male (MPEG 20618; Figs. 1–2) and a female (OMNH 37046; Fig. 3), collected on different days (respectively 3 and 22 March), were on the same fallen tree trunk. The male was first seen on the trunk, disappeared into a hole, and emerged again later on. The female had its head sticking out of the hole. Another male (OMNH 37047) was on a relatively small log (about 12 cm diameter) basking in a small patch of sunlight and then ran into a hole, from where it was dug out. MPEG 20619, a female, was observed on a thick vine close to the ground and disappeared into a hole in the vine. This vine was cut open and the animal was inside a relatively small space, completely pressing itself there; in spite of all the cutting, it didn't move from the hole, except when it was forced to (by opening the vine).

The last specimen collected (MPEG 20620), on 17 April, was a female. It was observed partially out of a hole at the top of a vine (about 40 cm high) rising from the ground; Fig. 4). Excavating the vine, we found two eggs at the bottom (Fig. 5). These were kept in the laboratory of Museu Paraense Emílio Goeldi, after returning to Belém-PA, and they hatched on the 26th and 29th

July (Fig. 6), measuring (snout-vent + tail length) 38 + 34 mm (MPEG 20630) and 34 + 29 mm (MPEG 20631).

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REFERENCES

Duellman W.E. 2005. Cusco Amazônico: The Lives of Amphibians and Reptiles in an Amazonian Rainforest. Comstock Publishing Associates, Ithaca and London.

Fritts T.H. 1974. A multivariate evolutionary analysis of the Andean iguanid lizards of the genus *Stenocercus*. *Memiors San Diego Society of Natural History* 7:1–89.

Meede U. 1984. Herpetologische Studien über Echsen (Sauria) in einem begrenzten Gebiet des Tropischen Regenwaldes in Peru: morphologische Kriterien, Autökologie und Zoogeographie. Artenliste der Reptilien im Untersuchungsgebiet. Doctoral Dissertation, Universität Hamburg.

Mertens R. 1942. Amphibien und Reptilien I. (Ausbeute der Hamburger Südperu-Expedition). Pp 277–287 in

Titschack E. (Ed.), *Beitrage zur Fauna Perus, Band II (1)*. Verlag Gustav Fischer, Jena.

Ribeiro-Junior M.A. 2015. Catalogue of distribution of lizards (Reptilia: Squamata) from the Brazilian Amazonia. I. Dactyloidae, Hoplocercidae, Iguanidae, Leiosauridae, Polychrotidae, Tropiduridae. *Zootaxa* 3983:1–110.

Vitt L.J., Avila-Pires T.C.S. 1998. Ecology of two sympatric species of *Neusticurus* (Sauria: Gymnophthalmidae) in the western Amazon of Brazil. *Copeia* 1998:570–582.

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Figure 1 - 2 Male *Stenocercus roseiventris*, MPEG 20618, in dorsolateral and ventral views.

Figure 3. Female *S. roseiventris* (OMNH 37046) sticking out of a hole.

Figure 4. Vine with hole where the female *S. roseiventris* MPEG 20620 and the eggs were found. The hole is c. 40 cm from the ground, with an inner diameter of c. 3.5 cm.

Figure 5. Eggs of *S. roseiventris* shortly after they were collected.

Figure 6. One of the two newly hatched *S. roseiventris* (MPEG 20630–31).